

THE TYPE OF RIDDLES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the riddle, which is a paremic genre, and its classification, description, and importance in forming the thinking and speech of elementary school students are discussed.

Riddle is one of the most common genres in world and Uzbek folklore. They can be used effectively to improve students' connected speech. Riddle is one of the ancient and traditional genres of folk art and has a special educational value. Riddles, like other genres of folklore, reflect customs and traditions of our people, spiritual, moral and aesthetic views. As a unique form of artistic perception of life, riddles reflect a person and the world around him by means of various metaphors, similes, comparisons, comparisons, and questions. In this respect, it is an extraordinary phenomenon in the development of human artistic thinking, in which a fragment of life that appears in the image is realized through the answers to the riddle. Such a general characteristic of the poetic nature of the genre applies to the riddles of all nations. Puzzle is an international genre. At the same time each a people's riddle is unique as an expression of that people's way of life, original, attractive and unique. Two objects, things, and events that are similar in terms of shape, function, action, and condition, and have similar signs characteristic of the other a question or a task given in a poetic or prose structure, aimed at finding it, is called a riddle. For example, let's take the riddle "Take a piece of paper, take it to the world." In this, the full moon and the halfmoon were compared to each other and it was determined that they are similar in terms of shape. Thus, the answer to the riddle - a very beautiful and appropriate migration of the moon - patir was found. Taking into account that the moon is an extremely rich source of food for man, and the moon illuminates the dark night, and both situations are aimed at humanity, there is a great spiritual affinity between them also becomes clear. The term "find" is made by adding the formative suffix "-ish" to the command verb "find" and adding the form "- moq" to it with the term genre. Riddles in different districts of our republic, according to the local characteristics and dialects of those places, are various such as puzzle, jummok, jumok, topmacha, topar chopchak, top-top, top-top chopchak, matal, masala, ushuk. is also expressed by but at present "finding" is the only

scientific as a literary term, the rest remained used in narrow circles and in the speech of some elderly people. Riddle-telling also had strict traditions and specific procedures. Telling the riddle mainly on winter nights is his past shows that there were certain prohibitions in its execution. At least two people, two groups or a riddle for the performance of the puzzle there should be those who say it and solve it, find the answer. to find as soon as the answer is found, the next ones will be told. That's why telling riddles is intelligence and intelligence at this time has become a means of competition, fun, entertainment. Among the people, "He was a tall dwarf, he knocked him down" (sleep), "Taller than a horse. There are very common riddles such as "Less than a dog" (saddle), "I spread cotton on a blue shirt" (sky and stars), "Snow does not stand on a pile" (eggs), and the answer to them is immediately found. But there are also riddles that are difficult to find the answer to, even people with a lot of life experience think. In such cases, additional information is provided that facilitates finding the answer, that is, finders of the answer from the speaker, "alive or inanimate?" they asked. Even then, if it becomes difficult to find an answer, "hard or soft?", "bitter, sweet?", "how is it?", "where is it?" When the answer is not found, "shahar" is used to embarrass the person who did not find the answer. Riddle is strictly prohibited the shame of being, the desire to avoid being insulted, to the riddle-telling game to get to know the participants a lot, to constantly improve their intellectual abilities encouraged. The derogatory words in "Shahar Bergan" were written by the participants in it did not hurt them either, on the contrary, there was an upliftment of spirit and cheerfulness in the circle, which caused them to laugh and be happy. Riddles are created on the basis of conditional hidden speech, the basis of which is related to the ancient beliefs and imaginations of people, the level of knowledge and perception of the world. The main part of Uzbek folk riddles is metaphorical, that is, one the characteristic of the object is conditional on another object similar to it make up riddles based on decay. Another type of Uzbek folk riddles are interrogative (question) riddles. The growth of objects in such riddles signs are not compared with each other, but specific questions and specific tasks are put before the finder. The answer in metaphorical riddles in such riddles, if it consists only of the name of the hidden object the answer is broadly interpreted. There are also very complex versions of interrogative (question) riddles.

There are other types of Uzbek folk riddles in which numbers are involved, that is, one or another thing and event is puzzled with the help of these numbers. Similarities between things and events are taken into account, of course. For example:

Bir daraxtda o'n ikki shoxa,
Har shoxada o'ttiz yaproq,
Yaprog'ining bir yoni qora, bir yoni oq

The answer to this riddle is one year, twelve months and thirty days and nights. There are other examples of riddles in the repertoire of our people, the answers of which are obtained by counting and calculating. An example: "While a flock of geese was flying, one goose came to them and said: - Hey, hundred geese, how are you?" Then one of them: - We are not a hundred geese. And if we amount to a goose, and half of us and half of ours, then if you join us, we will be a hundred geese, he said. How many geese are in the air?' Answer: 36 (36 + 36+18 + 9 + 1 - 100).

Such examples can be called masala-riddles. But they are extremely rare among the people. Uzbek folk riddles riddle-proverb, riddle-game, riddle-say quickly, riddle-song, there are also types such as riddle-tale. But their examples are endless is a minority. So, Uzbek folk riddles are very thematically rich and colorful. The nature of the country's social and household life of our people, There is no area of geography, ecology, flora and fauna, man and the universe, which are more beautiful, more compact and dense let there be no riddles. Earth and sky, rivers and lakes, mountains and rocks, groves and forests, orchards and vast fields, household appliances and tools, thunder and lightning, floods and dark and light, moon and seasons, animal and plant world, school supplies and musical instruments, modern technology and equipment, man and him passed down from generation to generation, making many riddles about the surrounding environment, It is said to our days. People's diary in riddles life, behavior and way of life, belief, imagination and outlook on the world are reflected. At the same time, historical events, social-political issues, class relations are also partially expressed. Riddles have been created throughout the ages. Something new to social life and with the introduction of events, riddles were also created about them. The rise of industry and agriculture, the development of science and culture during the Shura period found its artistic expression in new riddles. As a result, a series of riddles were created about the airplane, train, car, tram, tractor, gramophone, radio, television, satellite, telephone, light bulb that entered our life:

Qush emas, qanoti bor,
Chiroyli savlati bor.
Uchsa lochin yetolmas,
Tolmas zo'r quvvati bor. (*Samolyot.*)
It's not a bird, it has wings
He has a beautiful appearance.
The falcon cannot fly.
He has enormous power. (Airplane.)

The services of individual creators were great in the creation of new riddles. There are certain riddles created by such artists part of it has become popular among children. Riddles have a prose or poetic form in terms of structure. Prose riddles are a minority compared to riddles in poetic structure is enough. In poetic riddles, all the aspects of the form of the poem, such as stop, weight, rhyme, etc. Are fully followed. For example:

To'rt oyoqli,
Temir tuyyoqli. (*Ot.*)
Four-legged,
Iron hooves. (A horse.)
Or:
To'rtdir uning oyog'i,
Temir mixli tuyog'i,
Manzilga etishtirar,
Toshdan qattiq tuyog'i. (*Ot.*)
He has four legs,
Iron-studded hoof,

Delivers to the address,

Hard hoof made of stone. (A horse.)

The question and answer part of puzzles can be single-component (one question-answer, one subject) or multi-component (multiple question-answer, multiple subjects). The rhythmic consistency of the riddles, the artistic tone, the meaning of the rhymes It is distinguished by its abundance and diversity. Artistic image tools such as metaphor, metonymy, exaggeration, simile, qualification and many others are in them provides artistry. The variety of alliteration and repetition, and the various twists and turns make the riddles resonant and emotional. increased even more. All of these combined together ensured their long-lasting memory. Riddles had a beneficial effect on the development of literature and art. They are in the history of our literature, it was of great importance in the emergence and development of lyrical genres such as chistan, problem, muvashshakh, tarikh. Today, riddles have a great educational and educational value. They expand the scope of thinking of our children and youth, increase their ingenuity and is an important aesthetic tool for developing the ability to discuss. Expanding the scope of students' thinking by means of riddles, to strengthen observation and resourcefulness, intelligence, logical thinking reasoning ability can be developed, and logical thinking will lead to further development of students' speech. Simile, contrast, compare, Genre features of riddles, such as understanding conditional sentences, are children quickly attracts attention. Riddles are extremely compact, with internal and external rhyme, vital children learn them very quickly and have a long memory they will heal. Therefore, riddles can be effectively used in the development of students' oral and written speech in primary grades. Especially the children who are puzzled by organizing a riddle game in class persistence pays off. In this way, it is possible to increase the students' interest in the lesson. It is also possible to explain words with the help of riddles. For this purpose, the words from the language are selected and brought to the attention of the readers. Beginning with the following riddles in the Reading Book if used as didactic material to explain pairs of words:

Ko'zi bor, kiprik qoqmas,

Qanoti bor, uchmas hech.

Oyog'i yo'q, yo'l bosar

Suv ichida *erta-kech*. (22-bet).

Again:

O'xshar *qovun-tarvuzga*,

Sip-silliq kiygan to'ni.

Ichi olov, zar rangda,

Pishirib yeysan uni. (122-bet).

It seems that it is impossible to develop the thinking skills of builders Riddles are important in teaching activities and are the most convenient is one of the methodological tools. One of the things that are found depending on how many symbols are displayed, the answer to the riddle will be found. For this purpose, it is necessary to compare things with each other, to conduct a deep and comprehensive observation necessary. Riddles, like proverbs, are learned in relation to given topics. In this case, students should complete the following tasks according to

1. Telling the answer to the riddle based on what signs were found give
2. Say riddles similar to the given riddle:
 - 1) It is tall and has seven floors.
 - 2) Tones floor - floor,
One grain is one basket.
When it comes to the table,
Both dip and salad.
3. The similarities and differences of the riddles given above isolate and interpret.
Why the reader
The answer to the first riddle is an onion.

by clearly and completely proving that the latter is cabbage based on evidence attempt to give at the same time the improvement of speech skills, o power expansion of the scope of creative thinking, formation of speaking skills will bring. Riddle is an ancient genre, not only for young children, but also for adults in forming the generation's thinking, logical thinking, and speech, but also in writing It is also of great importance for the development of literature.

References:

1. Elly Kongas Maranda, "Riddles and puzzles": Introduction." American Journal of Folklore,89.
2. Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language, Tashkent. State Scientific Publishing House.5-vol.-p. 432.
3. Miaja, M. (2008). Riddle. Meaning and survival. Spain: Miguel de Servantes Virtual Library.
4. Maksudov H. "Don't pay attention to the one who says words, pay attention to the words. Yoshlik journal, 2018, issue 1. - p. 35.
5. Abdullayev J. Lexical and semantic features of Uzbek folk riddles: Abstract of the dissertation of the candidate of philological sciences. Tashkent, 1993.- p. 8.
6. Uzbek riddles. Tashkent: O'qituvchi, 1991. - p. 3
7. Qobulova U.S. The relationship of integral and differential semantics in the metaphorical text (on the example of the Uzbek folk riddle) Abstract of the dissertation. Tashkent, 2017. - p.12
8. Saparniyazova M. Syntactic-semantic features of Uzbek folk riddles: Abstract of the dissertation of the candidate of philological sciences. Tashkent, 2005. - p. 14.